

Andrew Williamson Wolfson Fellow 1968-9

Initial report on research progress September to November 1968

I arrived in Iran on the 25 August. Five weeks were taken up in practical preparations for field work and in repairs to my Land Rover.

From the 31 ^{September} October until the 7th November I was working on my survey of Islamic sites 1) In the region between Yazd and Kirmān.

2) The Northern routes from Shiraz to Kirmān.

I found the Kirmān plains surprisingly disappointing. Very few of the numerous sites I visited in these qanāt irrigated areas was of more than slight antiquity. The sites recorded by Muhammad Ayūb Khan surveyor to Sir Aurel Stein who conducted a detailed survey over five months in 1932 were almost exclusively post-mediaeval. Once out of the region of extensive qanāt irrigation and into Fars a more satisfactory pattern of sites of all sizes and periods began to emerge. My work necessarily concentrated on the Early Islamic period for which we have a ceramic chronology above all from Sīrāf and also from sites like Būst in Afghanistan. However, I have tried not to neglect any site of later date. The pottery collected on prehistoric mounds has been handed over to Mr. William Sumner of the University of Pennsylvania for study. In all over 110 mounds were recorded. I have also worked on standing monuments with special emphasis on caravanserais. I have noted inscriptions in six and have made measured plans of three besides making sketch plans of others.

My most important discovery to date has been the early Islamic site of Sīrjān which occupies a crucial position on the land route from Fars to Sind and also on several routes from the Persian Gulf inland. The mediaeval city situated on a great plain in Western Kirmān was capital of the Province, and although contemporary with Sīrāf was considerably larger and more populous. Today the site occupies an area of three kilometres by two. The surface pottery provides a unique combination of Islamic and Chinese sherds found at Sīrāf associated with a wide range of East and North Eastern Iranian wares. The pottery kilns unlike those at Sīrāf seem to have produced a wide variety of distinctive glazed wares.

I have deposited a fuller account of the site with Mr. Stronach together with a